

The teacher instructed the students to search Medline for articles related to systematic evaluation of diabetic foot and randomized controlled trials. The key words were "Diabetic foot or diabetic trauma and (Review or RCT)", and the subjects were limited to human body. The language is also limited to English. After preliminary screening, we selected the literature on diabetic foot, and provided a list of references (as follows), with the purpose of training students on how to obtain evidence-based medicine evidence on the treatment of diabetic foot.

References

1. Prevention and treatment of diabetic foot ulcers. Lim JZ, et al. J R Soc Med. 2017. PMID: 28116957 Free PMC article. Review.
2. Diabetic Foot Infections. Mills JP, et al. Michigan Medicine University of Michigan. 2019. PMID: 31967768 Free Books & Documents. Review.
3. Mesenchymal Stem Cells Improve Healing of Diabetic Foot Ulcer. Cao Y, et al. J Diabetes Res. 2017. PMID: 28386568 Free PMC article. Review.
4. A systematic review and meta-analysis of adjunctive therapies in diabetic foot ulcers. Elraiyah T, et al. J Vasc Surg. 2016. PMID: 26804368 Free article. Review.
5. Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy for the Treatment of Diabetic Foot Ulcers: A Health Technology Assessment. Health Quality Ontario. Ont Health Technol Assess Ser. 2017. PMID: 28572866 Free PMC article. Review.
6. Ozone therapy for diabetic foot. Kushmakov R, et al. Med Gas Res. 2018. PMID: 30319766 Free PMC article. Review.
7. Low-level laser therapy and Calendula officinalis in repairing diabetic foot ulcers. Carvalho AF, et al. Rev Esc Enferm USP. 2016. PMID: 27680049 Free article. Clinical Trial. English, Portuguese.
8. Evaluation of diabetic foot infection in nuclear medicine. Heiba S, et al. Q J Nucl MedMol Imaging. 2017. PMID: 28497940 Free article. Review.
9. Evaluation of negative-pressure wound therapy for patients with diabetic foot ulcers: systematic review and meta-analysis. Liu S, et al. Ther Clin Risk Manag. 2017. PMID: 28458556 Free PMC article. Review.

10. Implementation of foot thermometry plus mHealth to prevent diabetic foot ulcers: study protocol for a randomized controlled trial. Lazo-Porras M, et al. *Trials*. 2016. PMID: 27094007 Free PMC article. Clinical Trial.